

Supplementary Figure 1

Percentage of late-night salivary cortisol and cortisone samples exceeding the reference change value (RCV) during each day of liquorice intake and washout (wo) days. □ low-dose liquorice group; ▒ medium-dose liquorice group; ■ high-dose liquorice group.

